

Transcribing the Untranscribable: Automating Recognition of Text and Image in Multimodal Medieval Manuscripts from Law to Divination

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Introduction: The Limits of Sequential Transcription Models

The transcription of medieval manuscripts is a foundational task for the humanities, yet it remains a bottleneck for historical research. Over the past decade, specialised Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) models have achieved remarkable success, with platforms like Transkribus significantly accelerating large-scale digitisation of archival collections (Kahle et al. 2017)¹. However, a significant portion of our medieval documentary heritage remains largely inaccessible to these methods: **complex artifacts where meaning is inextricably linked to non-linear layouts, glosses, illustrations, and diagrams.**

Current HTR systems are built on the fundamental assumption of a linear and sequential² reading order. This paradigm collapses when confronted with multimodal medieval documents – see for instance Heiles (2018) for the divinatory genre of *sortes* text³ – resulting in garbled or entirely unusable transcriptions that misrepresent the essential nature of the artifact.

Multimodal Large Language Models (MLLMs) are an emerging generation of AI systems that **simultaneously process and integrate visual and textual information**, enabling richer context-aware reasoning (Wu et al. 2023). This paradigm has the potential to overcome long-standing limitations, enabling not only the accurate transcription of previously "untranscribable" manuscripts in terms of HTR but also the generation of rich, structured data for modern scholarly editions.

State of the Art and Research Gap: The Blind Spot of Non-Linearity and Non-Sequentiality

Technological and theoretical advances have methodologically impacted all phases of the scholarly editing workflow (for an overview of such developments, from collation to stemmatic analysis, data modelling, hermeneutics and visualisation we refer to, among others: Haentjens Dekker and Middell 2011; Roelli 2020; Van Zundert 2015; Bleier et al. 2018; Kuczera 2020; Andrews 2023; Haentjens Dekker and Birnbaum 2017; Cugliana et al. 2024). Scholars have also increasingly directed their attention to **multimodality**, showing how scholarly editing needs to address more than "just" text (Gengnagel 2024).

While HTR systems have reached impressive accuracy levels for transcription of linear texts (Li et al. 2022), the most recent wave of research has clearly demonstrated the potential of MLLMs like GPT-4o (OpenAI et al. 2024) and Gemini-2.5-Flash (Comanici et al. 2025) for historical document analysis. Through clever prompt engineering or in hybrid workflows, these models can outperform specialised systems in both accuracy and efficiency (Humphries et al. 2024; Greif, Griesshaber and Greif 2025; Kim et al. 2025).

However, in this body of research the transcription of manuscripts with non-linear and multimodal layouts – an obstacle for any HTR system – has been systematically avoided. This challenge reflects a broader, text-centric paradigm that has historically dominated the Digital Humanities, which however are increasingly engaging with multimodal research objects and methods (Birnbaum, Bonde and Kestemont 2017; Gengnagel 2024). A methodology for applying the power of MLLMs to the **automatic transcription of structurally challenging artifacts** is therefore missing. This is the research gap our work directly addresses.

Methodology: From Linear Text to Multimodal and Structural Analysis

Building upon existing research (which evolves day by day)⁴, **in the first phase of our work** we developed an **optimised MLLM workflow for linear texts**⁵: we first generated a baseline transcription using a Transkribus HTR model (Text-Titan 1) and then employed an MLLM to correct this draft. The MLLM's performance was guided by advanced prompt engineering that leveraged in-context examples and expert domain knowledge. This optimised pipeline consistently pushed transcription accuracy to new state-of-the-art levels. On a 14th-century German manuscript (Leipzig, UBL Ms. 688), it reduced the Character Error Rate (CER) to just 12.8% (a **35.4% relative improvement** over the baseline). On modern English cursive – the Bentham Papers (Milne 1962) – the final CER was reduced to a remarkable 2.0% (a **64.9% relative improvement**).

The second and most innovative phase of our work addressed the **automatic recognition of text and image in multimodal medieval manuscripts**. In our presentation we will show two qualitative case studies: (1) a workflow that prompts the MLLM to generate a textual transcription and structured descriptions of manuscript illuminations with explicit links to the text; (2) a multi-step pipeline for the transcription of non-linear and non-sequential layouts: through the MLLM's visual segmentation we create 'cut-outs' of the radial text wedges of a text in a circular layout (Fig. 3), then use another MLLM to programmatically determine the correct rotation for each segment, and finally apply our optimised hybrid transcription workflow from phase one to these now-linearised segments (Fig. 1)⁶.

Fig. 1: The two-pronged experimental methodology for (2). Plan A is a multi-step pipeline involving MLLM-based segmentation, automated rotation, normalisation, and the application of the optimised hybrid workflow. If segmentation fails, Plan B is enacted, which uses a few-shot approach on the complete page.⁷

Case Study 1: Multimodal Knowledge Extraction (*Sachsenspiegel*)

This case study investigates how MLLMs can be used for deep multimodal page analysis that moves beyond text transcription. The manuscript Wolfenbüttel, Herzog August Bibl., Cod. 3.1 Aug. 2° (W) represents one of the four il-

luminated manuscripts⁸ of the *Sachsenspiegel*, a medieval collection of laws and customs. Here the legal text is accompanied by a rich illustration program (Repgow 1993; Schmidt-Wiegand 1986).

We tasked an MLLM with three interconnected objectives:

- 1. Text Transcription:** accurately transcribing the textual passages.
- 2. Illustration Description and Classification:** generating a detailed, structured description of the image content and suggesting potential classifications using iconographic systems like Iconclass (van de Waal 1972–1985).
- 3. Linking Text and Image:** the most advanced task, requiring the model to establish explicit connections between text passages and pictorial elements, often guided by visual reference markers already present on the manuscript folio. The goal of this phase is the automated generation of structured data ideally suited for modelling in a knowledge graph, where text, images, and their relationships can be formally represented.

Fig. 2: A page from Wolfenbüttel, Herzog August Bibl., Cod. 3.1 Aug. 2°, Folio 10v, demonstrating the tight integration of text and illustration.

Case Study 2: Transcription of Non-Linear/Non-Sequential text (*sortes*)

Here we tackle the core challenge of transcribing structurally complex, non-linear documents. *Sortes* texts are a prime example; they are not designed for continuous reading but function as interactive divination tools (Heiles 2018). Their meaning is embedded in interactive reading paths (cf. Cugliana, Enns and Kuczera 2024), diagrams and images that form intricate layouts that confound any HTR model. We explore two primary strategies:

- 1. Advanced Visual Segmentation Pipeline:** Our primary workflow leverages the native visual segmentation

capabilities of newer models (e.g., Google's Gemini 2.5 series) to deconstruct the non-linear page. First, the MLLM is prompted to identify and create image "cut-outs" of the individual text wedges. Second, these isolated segments are passed to another MLLM call to programmatically determine the correct rotation angle to make the text horizontal. Finally, these normalised, now-linear segments are processed using the optimised hybrid transcription workflow established in the first phase of our work.

2. Instruction-Based Prompting: As a fallback for pages where automated segmentation may fail, we employ an end-to-end approach. This involves providing the MLLM with the full page image alongside a specific prompt that explains the document's logic and directs its focus, for instance: "Transcribe the text segment located at the 3 o'clock position of the wheel." This method tests the model's ability to follow complex spatial instructions without pre-processing. We organised our experiments using three different levels of layout complexity, with the page in Fig. 3 representing the lowest degree of complexity, with four wedges consisting of two subsections each. The other two levels included circular layouts divided into twelve wedges each comprising respectively two and four subsections.

Fig. 3: A page from a *sortes* manuscript (München, BSB Cgm 312, f. 135v), showcasing the circular layout that is illegible to standard HTR models⁹.

Discussion of Results

Our findings demonstrate the concrete advantages of these MLLM-centric workflows. For the *Sachsenspiegel*, the multimodal extraction successfully generated rich, plausible metadata. For instance, from a single illumination, the MLLM produced a detailed visual description ("a crowned figure...kneels...a bearded figure with a golden halo...seated on a throne"), suggested relevant Iconclass classifications (e.g., 11D3: Christ as judge), and correctly identified the visual correspondence marker (a large red letter 'G') that links the image to the legal text (Fig. 4). Furthermore, the MLLM-based transcription of the accompanying text yielded a CER of 12.0% and a WER of 32.2%, a 39.4% and 47.1% relative improvement, respectively, over a baseline HTR model. For the *sortes* texts, the advanced segmentation and rotation pipeline enabled the correct transcription of wheel segments that are entirely illegible to traditional HTR systems, successfully deconstructing the non-linear page into manageable, linear components where traditional systems failed entirely (Fig. 5).

Bounding Box: [270, 250, 480, 600]

Visual Description:

On the left, a crowned figure in a red cloak and green tunic kneels with hands raised in supplication. On the right, a bearded figure with a golden halo, dressed in a red cloak and blue tunic, is seated on a throne-like structure. This figure holds a sword upright in the right hand and a green book in the left. A large red letter 'G' is placed between the two figures.

Details: - Figures: 2 - Key Objects: crown, sword, book, halo, throne

Iconclass Classification: - 11D3: Christ as judge (relevance: 0.70) - 44B151: king(s) (relevance: 0.60) - 44B19: crown (regalia) (relevance: 0.60) - 41A3: sword (relevance: 0.70) - 49L8: book (relevance: 0.70)

Correspondence Marker: Letter: G (red) | Confidence: 0.90

Text Match: Matched Letter: G (confidence: 0.90) **Text:** "Got is selber lech dar fime is ym rech lip Dar inne fen fi lich alle vor di fen gerichte von gons halbin leuoi fi - das fi also richten alle gotis zc..."

Fig. 4: The image displays the structured metadata generated by the MLLM for an illumination on Folio 10v of the *Sachsenspiegel* manuscript (Wolfenbüttel, Herzog August Bibl., Cod. 3.1 Aug. 2^o).

Fig. 5: The coloured boxes illustrate how an MLLM's visual understanding is leveraged to identify and create 'cut-outs' of the individual, radial text wedges, which are subsequently programmatically rotated and linearised.

While, in case study 2, we obtained very good results with the 'low-complexity' dataset as shown in Fig. 5, we encountered difficulties with layouts belonging to the second and third categories. Specifically, high layout density challenged the automated segmentation¹⁰, necessitating a fallback to a visual-prompting workflow. While effective for intermediate layouts, this approach reached its limits with high-complexity cases; we will discuss these limits and the resulting 'frontier' of the method in our presentation.

In general, working with generative AI is not without its challenges. A central issue is "**hallucination**": the models occasionally invent information or over-interpret details not present in the source document (Bender et al. 2021; Boros et al. 2024). This necessitates careful human verification and underscores the role of AI as a "co-editor" or assistant, not as an autonomous researcher (Whittle et al. 2025).

Another critical topic is **reproducibility**. As this study primarily utilises proprietary models, which function as 'black boxes,' the exact replication of results presents a significant challenge for the scholarly community. We address this limitation by providing a transparent methodology and detailed documentation of our prompting strategies. The need to critically validate results and clearly state the technology's limitations is therefore not just a general principle, but a central aspect of our approach and a cornerstone of responsible scholarly practice in the age of AI.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that MLLMs have the potential to shift the focus from purely sequential text recognition to a holistic, visual-semantic document analysis. The ability of MLLMs to transcribe text and model visual relationships opens new horizons for the extraction of multimodal data.

In this context, our contribution aligns with advances in scholarly editing: in line with the increase in scalability of editorial work brought about by, for instance, automatic collation and computational stemmatology, multimodal transcription extends our capacity to render complex, often neglected sources, accessible for philological analysis.

Additional Material

Additional Material, Fig. A: An example of the geometric distortion resulting from applying an Equirectangular projection to the circular layout of the *sortes* manuscript (München, BSB Cgm 312, f. 135v). Note the significant horizontal stretching and loss of resolution, particularly in the text corresponding to the inner circumference of the wheel (bottom of the image). This artifact justifies the choice of the MLLM-based segmentation pipeline discussed in the main text

Additional Material, Fig. B: Visualisation for the text transcription pipeline. It begins with a standard HTR model generating a baseline transcription from the manuscript image. In the central 'Multimodal Post-Correction' stage, an MLLM is tasked with refining this baseline. Crucially, the MLLM's correction process is informed by three distinct inputs: (a) the baseline draft text to be corrected, (b) the original manuscript image for visual verification, and (c) an advanced prompt containing expert domain knowledge and in-context examples. By combining these elements, the MLLM can significantly reduce the error rate compared to the initial HTR output, producing a final, high-quality transcription.

Footnotes

1. Transkribus is utilized here solely as a representative provider for the HTR baseline. The pipeline is designed to be modular and platform-agnostic, capable of integrating with open-source HTR engines such as eScriptorium (Kiessling et al. 2019) or Kraken (Kiessling 2019).
2. Although these terms are often used interchangeably, with "linear" we specifically refer to the case in which text is written as a monodirectional chain of glyphs, in Western cultures usually going from left to right – we do not refer here to the concept of linearity in storytelling as used by, for instance, Ferreira and Ferreira (2021). With "sequential" we describe the phenomenon according to which the reading path is strictly connected to spatial adjacency: if segment B follows segment A, then the reading order will be A-B.
3. Such texts present cases of non-linearity, (for instance when text is written in circular pattern or when one word belongs to two different sentences/units at the same time) and are definitely non-sequential, as 1) the textual circles are continuously segmented and 2) the reading path is determined by interactive actions and not by adjacency.

4. Cf. Anita Lucchesi and Sean Takats's workshop at the international DH Conference in Lisbon in July 2025.

5. Tests with open-weights models (Mistral Small 3.2) demonstrated the pipeline's transferability: The method improved the model's performance from 49.4% CER (zero-shot) to 17.8%, surpassing the specialized HTR baseline.

6. An alternative method could be the application of geometric normalisation techniques, such as an Equirectangular projection, which 'unwraps' the circular text into a linear strip. While this method can be effective, it often introduces distortion by stretching the pixels of the inner circumference to match the width of the outer one. This can result in a loss of resolution detrimental to the accuracy of automatic transcription (see Additional Material, Fig. A for a visual example) - an issue our segmentation-based pipeline avoids by processing each text wedge in its native resolution. Further research could, however, explore hybrid approaches. For instance, an MLLM could be tasked with correcting the distorted output of a projection, or the initial layout detection could be automated. This could be achieved either with classical computer vision techniques like the **Hough Circle Transform** to find the wheel's boundaries, or by **directly prompting an MLLM to return the geometric parameters** (center_x, center_y, inner_radius, outer_radius) required for the unwrapping.

7. A detailed diagram of the text transcription pipeline is available as Additional Material, Fig. B.

8. Heidelberg, Universitätsbibliothek Heidelberg, Cod. Pal. germ. 164 (H), Oldenburg, Landesbibliothek Oldenburg CIM I 410 (O) and Dresden, SLUB, Mscr. Dresd. M.32 (D).

9. In particular, the text is non-linear, being circular and following multiple orientations, including text written upside down. Its non-sequentiality is well exemplified by the outer circle containing the names of the four pagan masters: After reading "Socrates mayster", the reader should not read the immediate following "Aristotiles Mayster" segment, but proceed with the internal part of Socrates' section.

10. Our error analysis differentiates between segmentation errors (visual localization), rotation errors, and pure transcription errors. The failure of the fully automated workflow at medium complexity, contrasted with the successful switch to explicit visual prompting, illustrates this distinction, as the primary bottleneck was localization rather than text recognition.

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